

Behaviour of Gases under the Influence of High Frequency Discharge. Ammonia and Hydrogen.

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Hiedmann (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1933, **A 164**, 20) observed that under the influence of high frequency discharge through hydrogen in degassed tubes of pyrex or silica, a condensible product which he thought to be silane, was obtained. Bhatt (a paper read in the Easter session of The South Indian Science Association, Bangalore 1934) contradicts this and shows that the product was water vapour. Bhatt worked with a 2 metres wave-length of high frequency magnetron. In the case of hydrogen he reports a disappearance of hydrogen which could be recovered only to about $\frac{2}{3}$ of the original quantity by degassing and baking out the tubes. In view of the above conflicting results it was thought interesting to publish the results of the present author, obtained as early as 1929.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

In an attempt to study the kinetics of the decomposition of ammonia at low pressures under the influence of electrode-less discharge by means of a high frequency oscillator, it was found that reproducible results could not be obtained due to some peculiar effect coming into play between the gas and the walls of the vessel. Hence the study of chemical reaction was abandoned and the behaviour of ammonia and hydrogen under the influence of the discharge was studied.

The High Frequency Oscillator.—Two LS₅ valves capable of carrying a filament current of 0.8 amp. each were connected up in parallel as shown in the diagram (Fig 1), with suitable inductances and chokes. The whole was mounted on a bakelite board with waxed pyrex glass tubes holding it in position on a well paraffined wooden base. The straight wires A, B, C, themselves formed the inductances. They were made of no. 20 copper wire, silver deposited. Extensive lecher wire measurements were made and though it was possible to get short waves of the order of 2 to 2.5 metres, vacuum tubes placed in the vicinity of the inductance could not be made to glow. Hence various types of inductances were tried. Those with the loops with ebonite separators proved useful in as much as the vacuum tube could be placed in the centre of the loop. One with two loops gave on lecher wire, waves of about 4.2 metres but discharge started with difficulty. Finally one with 4 loops was adopted since it was able to start a discharge in the vacuum tube placed at the centre, without any difficulty. The waves were of 10.5 metres in length and were used throughout the experiment. The reaction tube consisted of Pyrex tube 6" long and $\frac{3}{4}$ " in internal diameter, closed at one end and connected to a system of pumps and manometer. The drying tube contained lumps of baryta for the elimination of moisture instead of the usual phosphorus pentoxide. Pressures were measured with the special types of McLeod gauge and Pirani gauge was specially avoided since it was thought that a hot filament in the system would induce other effects.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preliminary.—Pure dry ammonia gas was led into the evacuated apparatus. According to the reaction $2\text{NH}_3 \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + 3\text{H}_2$, there ought to be only twice the amount of the original volume, even if complete decomposition had taken place. But however, a series of ex-

periments showed that under action of the discharge some times, the amount of gas in the tube was far in excess of that demanded by the above equation. Starting with 9.5×10^{-2} mm. of ammonia with a discharge (plate current 40 m.a.) for 300 min. there was 39.5×10^{-2} mm. of gas in the apparatus. The apparatus was next thoroughly exhausted, at the same time baking out in an electric furnace. While still under evacuation, the discharge was sent in (36 m. a. plate current; 2.8 m. a. grid current) till there was a constant pressure in the apparatus to 0.9×10^{-2} mm. This time, when again starting with 9.5×10^{-2} mm. of ammonia under similar conditions, 85.7×10^{-2} mm. of gas accumulated even in 20 minutes.

The experiments were then conducted with hydrogen instead of ammonia. Starting with 19.7×10^{-2} mm. of hydrogen under similar conditions of discharge as before, the pressure rose to 24.5×10^{-2} mm. in two hours and remained steady thereafter. The apparatus was then exhausted to 0.5×10^{-2} mm. and the discharge continued as before. In about 30 minutes there was evolution of gas to 3.1×10^{-2} mm. where it remained steady.

It is possible from the above that the walls of the highly exhausted tube would rapidly adsorb the gases let in and during the action of the high frequency discharge would be liberated exactly as would happen during the degassing of the vacuum tubes by baking out. The easily condensible and basic nature of ammonia would exhibit this behaviour to a more marked degree than hydrogen.

In order to test this idea, the exact amount of gas let in at a known pressure, and the volume of the apparatus including dead-space leads to pumps, etc., has to be known.

Calibration of the volume of the apparatus (including the dead space leads to pumps, etc).—A micro-burette with a levelling bulb as shown in Fig. 2. was attached to the apparatus. The volume of the capillary between the taps A and B including the capillary space in tap A was carefully calibrated. It was 0.0361 c.c. For the calibration of the volume of the whole apparatus nitrogen was taken as the reference gas. The apparatus was evacuated moderately and known volumes of nitrogen gas, as measured by the micro burette at atmospheric pressure, was let into the apparatus. From the reading of the McLeod gauge, the volume of the apparatus was calculated. Care was taken not to exhaust the apparatus too hard lest there should be adsorption of the gas by the evacuated walls of the vessel. A few results of the calibration are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Initial pressure in apparatus.	Amount of gas introduced at atmospheric pressure.	Final pressure in apparatus.	Volume of apparatus.
0.95 mm. $\times 10^{-3}$	0.0361 c.c.	7.56 mm. $\times 10^{-2}$	368.5
12.20	0.0361	19.44	337.0
31.00	0.1083	53.05	334.0
53.05	0.1083	75.17	335.0

The first result in this table shows a higher value since due to evacuation to a low degree, some gas must have gone into the walls of the vessels. The mean volume of the apparatus was taken as 335 c.c.

Experiments with Ammonia.

0.1083 C.c. pure dry ammonia at 669.6 mm. pressure were let into the apparatus which was evacuated previously to a pressure of 0.58×10^{-2} mm. The McLeod gauge showed only a pressure of 2.0×10^{-2} mm. whereas the calculated pressure ought to have been 21.66×10^{-2} mm. So nearly 90% of ammonia have been adsorbed by the walls of the vessel.

With a discharge (plate current 37 m.a. and grid current 2.3 m.a.) in 2 minutes, a further quantity was adsorbed and pressure fell to 0.71×10^{-2} mm. and remained steady thereafter. Again a further quantity of ammonia was introduced into the apparatus till the pressure was 6.5×10^{-2} mm. and the fall of pressure in presence of the discharge is shown in Table II.

TABLE II.

Surface of glass saturated previously with ammonia.

Time (min.)	...	0.0	0.5	30.0	70.0	100.0	160.0
Pressure (mm. $\times 10^{-2}$)	...	6.5	12.4	0.78	2.08	3.56	3.56

The above result with ammonia is capable of being almost exactly reproducible. The excess amount of ammonia is not adsorbed since the surface is already saturated with ammonia. Results in Table II suggest that the instant the discharge was started there has been

a sudden decomposition of ammonia giving a pressure of the resulting gas of 12.4×10^{-2} mm. In 30 minutes in the discharge, the whole of this nitrogen and hydrogen are adsorbed by the surface which is still free from these gases, leaving again an amount of ammonia of the order of 0.78×10^{-2} mm. in equilibrium with that adsorbed on the surface, before the experiment. A further continuation of the discharge expelled the nitrogen which is the least adsorbed on the surface in comparison with ammonia and hydrogen. In the above experiment it is evident that 5.79×10^{-2} mm. of ammonia decomposed under the influence of the discharge giving 11.69×10^{-2} mm. of a mixture of nitrogen and hydrogen, and after adsorption of hydrogen, left a residue of 2.85×10^{-2} mm. of nitrogen. This is in accordance with the stoicheometric equation for the decomposition of ammonia. In the absence of spectroscopic evidence as to the nature of the residual gas this conclusion appears plausible.

Experiments with Hydrogen.

The tube was thoroughly baked out under prolonged exhaustion and the apparatus was washed several times with hydrogen thereafter. Finally the apparatus was evacuated to a pressure of 0.19×10^{-2} mm. 0.0722 C.c. of hydrogen at 669.9 mm. pressure was introduced in the apparatus. The McLeod gauge showed a pressure of 14.34×10^{-2} mm. The calculated pressure is 14.44×10^{-2} mm. The following table records the effect of the discharge.

TABLE III.

Plate current = 45 m.a. Grid current = 3 m.a.

Time.	Pressure.	Time.	Pressure.
0'0 min.	14.34 mm. $\times 10^{-2}$	270'0 min.	2.83 mm. $\times 10^{-2}$
30'0	1.39	390'0	8.69
90'0	0.90	510'0	9.30
150'0	1.89	630'0	9.30
210'0	2.13		

At this stage when about $\frac{2}{3}$ of the original gas was desorbed under the prolonged influence of the discharge, the tube was baked out at about 400° for two hours. The apparatus was cooled and the pressure inside was 14.44×10^{-2} mm. The original quantity of the

gas was recovered. On subjecting it again to the high frequency discharge, the results in Table III could be repeated again. So hydrogen disappears almost completely under the influence of the discharge but in about 10 hours working, about $2/3$ of the original amount could be degassed. The whole amount is obtained by baking out the tube. This precludes the possibility of any new gas being formed.

FIG. 3.

The data presented in Fig. 3 are obtained from experiments conducted with 0.0722 c.c. of gas at 670.55 mm. at a pressure of 14.44×10^{-2} mm. in the apparatus. Curve A shows that the hydrogen is rapidly adsorbed in the first 30 minutes, the pressure falls to a low value of 4.75×10^{-2} mm. after which degassing begins and goes on steadily except for a slight fatigue when 6.73×10^{-2} mm. are reached and after which at the end of 14 hours the whole of the hydrogen is recovered. The graph shows that the initial drop is far lower when the apparatus is previously heated under vacuum than otherwise. The fatigue during degassing is obtained again at a pressure of 6.75×10^{-2} mm. If the tube is baked out at 400° , the original amount of gas is expelled. The process of adsorption and desorption can again be repeated in the presence of the high frequency discharge. The existence of a stop during degassing at 6.73×10^{-2} mm. cannot be explained without further investigation.

CONCLUSIONS.

From the foregoing experiments the following conclusions have been drawn.

1. Ammonia is greatly adsorbed by the walls of highly evacuated glass tubes as compared with hydrogen.
2. When the walls of the vessel are saturated with reference to ammonia, the extra gas put in decomposes at once into nitrogen and hydrogen. In the presence of the discharge the hydrogen is adsorbed leaving off nitrogen.
3. The adsorption of ammonia appears to be irreversible under the influence of the electrodeless discharge, but hydrogen could be adsorbed as well as desorbed from the surface in a quantitative manner by the discharge.
4. The adsorption of hydrogen under the influence of the discharge is like the degassing of the tube by baking at 400° . In both the cases the whole of the gas put in could be recovered back.
5. In no case was obtained more gas than was put in. The possibility of any new gas formation seems to be remote.

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